

COREnext Solutions: Training Pill

27.11.2025 | corenext.eu

Over the past months, COREnext has advanced a number of demonstrations showcasing how its architectural framework and digital components can support the development of secure, adaptable and high-performance communication systems. From trust-aware IoT management to resource-optimised network services, these demonstrations illustrate the practical application of COREnext technologies and highlight the progress being made across the project's technical work.

In this issue, readers will also find an overview of the latest scientific publications produced by the consortium, offering further insight into the research directions, experimental findings and methodologies shaping the project's outcomes.

COREnext Demonstrations

[Demonstrating the M3 Platform - Tackling Hardware Vulnerabilities with Trusted Communication](#)

At a recent demonstration, Michael Roitzsch from the Barkhausen Institut presented the M3 hardware and operating system architecture, designed to tackle the increasing risk of hardware-level vulnerabilities in modern processors and accelerators. As these components grow in complexity, they are more prone to security flaws, as shown by high-profile cases such as vulnerabilities in Intel processors. The M3 platform aims to provide a more resilient structure capable of withstanding such attacks.

[Read more](#)

[AI-Enabled Physical Security Using Radio Frequency Fingerprinting](#)

As part of the COREnext project, researchers demonstrated an AI-enabled physical layer security solution based on radio frequency (RF) fingerprinting – a technique that enables the authentication of wireless devices by exploiting subtle, hardware-based signal characteristics. The demonstration showcased how machine learning can identify, authenticate, and protect

against impersonation attacks in communication network systems.

[Read more](#)

[Securing FPGA Offloading in the Cloud](#)

As part of the COREnext project, researchers at Nokia have demonstrated a secure FPGA offloading framework for cloud computing environments. The demonstration showcases how data processing tasks can be safely offloaded from CPUs to FPGAs (Field Programmable Gate Arrays) in containerised, cloud-native architectures, such as those using Kubernetes and Docker, without compromising data confidentiality.

[Read more](#)

[High-Datarate Interconnects over Plastic Optical Fibre - Advancing Next-Generation Connectivity in COREnext](#)

Within the COREnext project, one of the recent demonstrations led by INFINEON has explored how plastic optical fibre can support high-speed data transfer inside future communication systems. The work focuses on a high-rate data link

operating in the H-Band, using a Plastic Multimode Fibre (PMF) and an in-package PMF coupler designed specifically for this frequency range. This approach offers a different route toward compact and efficient data interconnects, reducing dependency on traditional materials while supporting the scalability required for emerging workloads.

[Read more](#)

[Validating Secure Sub-THz Point-to-Point Links](#)

As part of the COREnext project, researchers at IMEC have demonstrated a point-to-point sub-terahertz (sub-THz) communication link operating at 140 GHz, validating both its performance and security. The demonstration illustrates how high-frequency wireless communication can deliver ultra-high data rates while maintaining robustness against eavesdropping — a key step toward enabling next-generation 6G systems.

[Read more](#)

[Trust Evaluation and IoT Management](#)

As part of the COREnext project, Wings ICT Solutions has developed and demonstrated an innovative Trust Evaluation and IoT Management mechanism — a digital component

designed to optimise the deployment of workloads across Internet of Things (IoT) devices based on their trustworthiness. This work forms part of the project's broader objective to create secure, adaptive, and high-performance digital infrastructures for next-generation communication systems.

[Read more](#)

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High Data Rate Interconnects Over Plastic Fiber 6:18

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Don't Miss Out On Our Demonstration Brochure!

TrustEvaluation and IoT Management demo

The demo showcases how the Trust Manager evaluates IoT devices in real time using trust metrics, updating each device's trust index dynamically. Based on these values and resource availability, the Trust Manager Orchestrator assigns tasks to the most reliable and capable devices, ensuring secure and efficient operation.

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The Trust Evaluation Function calculates a trust score (0 to 1) for each device class by normalising key metrics, applying weights based on importance, and adjusting for data age using exponential decay. This ensures recent data has greater influence, with the final score derived from a weighted average of the adjusted metrics.

EXPECTED RESULTS

- Calculated trust scores of devices
- A graph of trustworthiness vs number of tasks/workloads
- Evaluation of the execution time

WORKING TOWARDS END-TO-END TRUSTWORTHINESS

COREnext believes that trustworthiness needs to be a native part of 6G as anticipated applications will merge the digital and physical worlds.

The goal of the project is to strengthen the mobile communication ecosystem in Europe by addressing key challenges associated with beyond 5G use cases.

Activities stretch from radio hardware innovation to compute architectures – with trustworthiness in focus.

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European core technologies for the next generation - communication - computing hardware

Eavesdropper avoidance

This sub-THz demonstrator showcases how beam-steering technology can be used to enhance link security.

The system focuses on preventing eavesdropping by dynamically controlling signal direction. It offers an interactive experience for users to engage directly with the beam-steering process.

The system integrates MATLAB baseband signal processing with analogue beam-steering transceivers, featuring four independent RF front-ends and antennas for real-time beam control. An interactive interface enables live visual monitoring and operation.

Beam-steering at sub-THz frequencies enhances link security by lowering interception risks. Real-time user interaction demonstrates practical beam control, improving public understanding of physical-layer security and offering a scalable solution for future high-frequency wireless networks.

The demo shows how real-time beam-steering at sub-THz frequencies enhances link security, offering hands-on insight into practical physical-layer cybersecurity for future networks.

High datarate interconnects over plastic fiber

This demo is based on the concept of high speed data link for communication via PMF in the H-Band, and PMF coupler in package at H-Band.

- MMICs in eWLB package, assembled on PCB
- H-band PMF coupler realized in package
- H-band PMF fiber and holder

This is the first in-package PMF coupler demonstrated in the H-Band, offering a compact, low-loss, and cost-effective solution for high-speed data links. It enables faster communication with reduced energy consumption, supporting future applications such as next-generation data centres.

The goal of the demonstration is to prove the concept of communication via PMF in H-Band.

RF Fingerprint for Wireless Network Security

The Radio Fingerprint demonstrator offers an interactive look at how AI can use subtle hardware impairments in radio devices to enhance cellular communication security. By learning these unique signatures, machine learning models can identify authorised transmitters and detect unauthorised access attempts.

The demo uses machine learning models trained on transmitter non-idealities to classify radio devices in real time. It employs real hardware to transmit authentication signals and identifies authorised devices based on physical signal characteristics, without decoding the data.

The system enables device identification using hardware-specific features, without cryptographic keys. It lowers the risk of unauthorised access from devices with identical chipsets and provides a low-complexity, efficient method to enhance physical-layer security.

The demonstration introduces RF fingerprinting and shows how machine learning can authenticate radio devices securely and efficiently. It highlights how physical-layer security can complement traditional cryptography to strengthen wireless network trustworthiness.

Trustworthy Computer Platform M³

M³, developed at Barkhausen Institut, is a modular and secure operating system built on a tiled hardware architecture. Each component runs on a separate, isolated tile, following a security-by-design approach that limits the impact of potential compromises. This architecture enhances containment of untrusted software and hardware, strengthening trust in connected systems.

The platform provides hardware-level isolation between processing components in heterogeneous systems, enabling secure execution environments that mitigate hardware-induced vulnerabilities. Its adaptable architecture supports diverse, multi-vendor system configurations.

The architecture enhances system resilience by containing faults within individual hardware modules and reducing the risk of system-wide compromise through trusted execution zones. It supports secure, scalable design essential for future digital infrastructure.

The objective of this demonstration is to illustrate how hardware isolation strengthens the trustworthiness of complex digital systems. The M³ platform demonstrates a practical method for securing next-generation platforms by compartmentalising potential risks at the hardware level.

Secure Acceleration (FPGA)

The Secure Acceleration demonstrator showcases FPGA-based hardware acceleration for improved digital platform efficiency. It allows multiple tenants to securely share resources, using cryptographic components and key exchange protocols to protect sensitive data, such as health information, during processing.

The FPGA acceleration board supports secure multi-tenant resource sharing, featuring cryptographic modules and secure key exchange protocols. It enables real-time, privacy-preserving data processing in sensitive areas such as healthcare.

The demonstrator enables efficient and secure hardware acceleration for multiple users or applications, ensuring data confidentiality with robust cryptographic protection. It illustrates scalable, secure resource management for future digital infrastructures.

The goal of the demonstration is to show how sensitive data can be securely processed within shared hardware environments. It highlights a crucial advancement towards secure, efficient computing for digital platforms requiring hardware acceleration in multi-tenant, high-security contexts.

[Explore our brochure where all 6 demonstrations are described!](#)

COREnext believes that trustworthiness needs to be a native part of 6G as anticipated applications will merge the digital and physical worlds. The goal of the project is to strengthen the mobile communication ecosystem in Europe by addressing key challenges associated with beyond 5G use cases. Activities stretch from radio hardware innovation to compute architectures – with trustworthiness in focus.

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[A 66Gbps/5.5W RISC-V Many-Core Cluster for 5G+ Software-Defined Radio Uplinks](#)

With the scale-up of 5G and beyond, base stations face rising computing demands under tight latency and power constraints. We present a many-core cluster design featuring 1024 streamlined RISC-V cores with floating-point extensions and 4MiB shared memory. It supports software-defined processing of the 5G physical uplink shared channel, achieving throughput up to 302Gbps — around 10× higher than state-of-the-art processors. The cluster delivers competitive energy efficiency (2–41Gbps/W), completing end-to-end PUSCH processing in 1.7ms at under 6W, reaching 12Gbps/W.

[Read more](#)

[Sensitivity Analysis of mmWave Multiuser MIMO with Imperfect Analog Beamforming State Information](#)

This paper analytically examines the impact of imperfect beamforming (BF) information on analog-beamformed multiuser downlink MIMO systems. It derives approximations for average SINR and symbol error probability (SEP) under various BF error distributions and validates them through simulations for both partially and fully connected architectures. Results show that sub-degree BF accuracy, especially at the transmitter, is crucial, particularly as system load and antenna count increase. The study highlights the significant alignment challenges facing future mmWave systems using analog BF.

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[Conflict Management in Vector Register Files](#)

Vector processors' instruction set architecture works with vectors in a vector register file, which must manage multiple concurrent accesses. High utilization leads to access conflicts, causing performance degradation. Using a software model, we explore the impact and characteristics of these conflicts and methods to manage

them: avoidance, resolution, and mitigation. For avoidance, we examine static bank layouts and propose a dynamic one to address their limitations by assigning new registers a unique starting bank. For resolution, we compare arbitration algorithms and optimize round-robin for mixed-width arithmetic by prioritizing wide operands. For mitigation, we study operand queues of varying depths. Our solutions aim to improve vector processors' area efficiency by allowing shallower operand queues or reducing the number of banks, with a performance impact of 10% or less. These insights can also apply to other shared memory systems.

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